

Hierarchical Energy-aware Monitoring Framework for Sustainability of Packet-Optical Networks

W. Akbar¹, J. Vilchez¹, R. Muñoz¹, R. Vilalta¹, Ll. Gifre¹

¹ Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Castelldefels (Barcelona), Spain
e-mail: ricard.vilalta@cttc.es

Abstract: We present a hierarchical energy monitoring framework to systematically analyze energy consumption in computing, IP, and Optical networks. We demonstrated the framework on the laboratory testbed to validate the practicality and scalability. ©2024 The Authors.

1. Introduction

The advent of 6G networks demands a large amount of computing resources with high availability, resulting in increased energy consumption. Optimization of energy consumption is a top priority in 6G networks. By understanding energy consumption, one can build an algorithm to efficiently utilize network resources and optimally deploy routing policies [1]. This includes reconfiguring or powering off devices to save energy. Several authors have proposed monitoring frameworks with dedicated purposes. For example, [2] proposes a monitoring framework with a focus on estimating and acquiring various physical parameters of transmitted signals, link conditions, and component performance, including OSNR monitoring, ubiquitous power monitoring, or BER estimation. [3] proposed a machine learning-based optical performance monitoring module for the detection of anomalies in optical services. [4] presented the telemetry service only specific to optical network for the detection of soft failure recovery at the transceiver level. Thus, we need a granular energy monitoring system that can track and analyze energy consumption of networking devices, services, and operations [5]. Most of the efforts have not focused on energy consumption monitoring, but rather specific to use case. Therefore, we propose a novel approach in this regard.

This paper presents the implementation and demonstration of a hierarchical energy monitoring system for computing, IP, and Optical networks, consisting of a probing, storage, and visualization layer. Additionally, physical sensors are deployed on each device to measure energy consumption. An individual probing layer functionality is implemented for each network domain to extract energy consumption metrics. A time-series database is implemented in each network to gather domain specific metrics and another database for persistent storage. A visualization tool is implemented to analyze the energy consumption metrics in real-time to provide a single view of the whole system. All of these components are loosely coupled, making them ideal for as needed deployment. The paper demonstrates the operation of a monitoring system in a lab testbed scenario. A testbed consists of three networks: Computing, IP and Optical. A traffic generator is configured on datacenters to create end-to-end data traffic test at 10 Gb/s and 100 Gb/s. During the traffic test the energy consumption metrics are measured from the operating system API/protocol as well as from sensors to validate the accuracy of energy monitoring system. This experiment provides a path for possible machine learning based resource optimization algorithms to improve energy utilization.

Fig. 1: (a) Proposed architecture of hierarchical monitoring system. (b) Sequence diagram of proposed architecture

2. Hierarchical Monitoring Architecture for Computing, IP and Optical Networks

Fig. 1 (a) shows the proposed hierarchical monitoring architecture consists of domain specific and end-to-end monitoring modules. The monitoring system is deployed as standalone microservice deployment, providing an API for controller and orchestrator communication. However, this monitoring system can be deployed inside the controller as a part of complete package. There are three different types of network domains: Computing, IP, and Optical. Each has its own monitoring module, which has three services: visualization service to view the information, a storage service with two databases, and a domain specific exporter to extract and expose the information. There are two different types of exporters: hardware and software exporter. Hardware exporters read the metrics from the physical sensor deployed on each device. Software exporters read the metrics from the operating system API/protocols. Getting the information from both sources assists to validate the accuracy of the measurement. This domain specific deployment helps to improve the scalability of the proposed monitoring system. Fig. 1 (b) represents the flow of data from information extraction to visualization. For computing and IP domain the metrics are extracted from both sources' API and physical sensors. For optical networks, the metrics are extracted only from sensors. In the "Domain Monitoring Module," the diagram introduces the Node as a representation of a physical entity, such as server or device that generates monitoring data. The Node is monitored in two ways: from the physical sensor and Protocol/API, each one with its own exporter. The Exporter acts as an intermediary, facilitating the extraction of metrics from the Node and exposing them to Prometheus. Subsequently, the metrics are transmitted to Prometheus, which serves as the initial repository for temporary storage. The journey continues with a RemoteWrite operation, which involves both Prometheus and Mimir. Prometheus facilitates temporary storage, while Mimir takes on the role of remote storage, ensuring the durability and accessibility of the metrics. In the "E2E Monitoring Module", Prometheus once again handles temporary storage, while Mimir engages in persistent storage. Eventually, the destination for the metrics is Grafana, potentially for visualization and analysis, adding a layer of user-friendly interpretation to the monitoring system. This intricate flow of data illustrates the comprehensive monitoring infrastructure's ability to effectively handle and store metrics.

3. Use case validation and results

To fully understand the energy consumption of a network, it is essential to measure the energy consumption of each device under three condition: an ideal state, with normal load and with high load. Additionally, device specifications should be noted. The architecture diagram shows the scenario consisting of two datacenters (edge and core), two routers (router1 and router2), and two ROADMs (ROADM1 and ROADM2). The ROADM devices are connected to each other through a 5 km bidirectional optical link consisting of 2 fiber spools of Corning SMF-28 Ultra. Each gateway has a bidirectional optical link with a 100G QSFP28 transceiver to connect to ROADMs. ROADM1 is connected to gateway1 through 32x32 Glimmerglass transparent optical fiber. Similarly, ROADM2 is connected to gateway2 through a 32x32 Polatis optical fiber. Both routers are Edge-Core AS7315-27X CSR310 300G ONIE with Open Compute Network Operating Systems (OcNOS) from Infusion installed. Both datacenters have a ConnectX-6 NIC with QSFP28 transceivers at 1310nm. A connection between both datacenters, and routers is established through 10m bidirectional optical fiber. Scaphandre is an open-source monitoring agent that exposes the energy consumption metrics such as power, energy, and voltage. Scaphandre is deployed on datacenters (edge and core) as an exporter to expose the energy consumption metrics. SNMP, a widely used protocol for network management, presents all the device related metrics when configured with proprietary Management Information Base (MIB). Our routers use a proprietary MIB (IPI-CMM-CHASSIS-MIB) with Object Identifiers (1.3.6.1.4.1.36673.100.1.2.6) that provide energy consumption metrics. An SNMP exporter is configured with OID to extract power consumption metrics. The router command line interface (CLI) can be used to extract the power consumption metrics. A small piece of code can be used to periodically request power consumption metrics from the CLI. To generate a load on the nodes, a traffic generator (iperf3) is installed on both datacenters running Ubuntu operating system, the core datacenter runs a server applications and edge datacenter runs a client application. In the first instance, the server application starts and listens for the client's request. When the client application is initiated, the path will be established and generates data traffic. The path between the client and server application passes through all the intermediate nodes with preconfigured routes. Therefore, we validated the functionality and performance of the proposed monitoring architecture under different traffic loads. With no data traffic load (device is working on ideal state), with 10G/s and 100G/s data traffic loads, respectively.

Grafana, a visualization tool, displays the power consumption values extracted in real-time by the proposed monitoring system, as shown in Fig. 2. The power consumption values for computing and IP network are extracted from two sources: form physical sensors (in green) and API (in yellow and blue). For the Optical network, the power consumption value is extracted from physical sensors only. Fig. 2 (a) and (d) show the power consumption of the edge and core datacenter, respectively. There is a clear change in power consumption during the 10G and 100G data traffic tests, because the traffic generator is running on these devices. The impact of power consumption due to high data traffic is

Fig. 2: (a) and (d) Measured power consumption of edge and core datacenter from sensor (green) and API (yellow), respectively. (b) and (e) Measured power consumption of router 1 and 2 from sensor (green) and API (blue), respectively. (c) and (f) Measured power consumption of ROADM 1 and 2 from sensor (green), respectively.

clearly visible, with the power consumption of a device more than double when generating 100G data traffic. Fig. 2 (b) and (e) show the power consumption of router 1 and 2, respectively. The 100G test shows clearly visible changes in power consumption, while the 10G test shows a slight increase, because the advanced router is energy efficient and usually operates on a stable power supply. Figure 2 (c) and (f) show the power consumption of ROADM devices. Power consumption remains the same during both test because the laser in optical device is always active and operates on a stable power supply. Our results show that the measurements taken through the hardware and software exporters are similar. Which validates the accuracy of measurements taken from both sources. We suggest using Scaphandre to measure the energy consumption of datacenters on a cloud network because it provides good estimate of complete host energy usage and the energy consumption of a single or a group of processes/services. Similarly, SNMP/CLI-based exporter provides accurate energy consumption of routers. This research will help better understand the energy consumption of the entire network and pave the way for improvement in resource optimization and routing algorithms.

4. Conclusions

We have successfully demonstrated the deployment and performance of hierarchical energy monitoring system. The proposed monitoring system provides a pathway for future energy-efficient routing algorithms and improves the performance of resource management schemes.

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References

1. Bomin Mao, Fengxiao Tang, Yuichi Kawamoto, and Nei Kato. Ai models for green communications towards 6g. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 24(1):210–247, 2021.
2. S. Yan et al. Multilayer network analytics with sdn-based monitoring framework. *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, 9(2), 2017.
3. C. Natalino and other. Scalable and efficient pipeline for ml-based optical network monitoring. In *OFC*, 2023.
4. Francesco Paolucci, Andrea Sgambelluri, Moises Felipe Silva, Alessandro Pacini, Piero Castoldi, Luca Valcarenghi, and Filippo Cugini. Peer-to-peer disaggregated telemetry for autonomic machine-learning-driven transceiver operation. *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.*, 14(8):606–620, Aug 2022.
5. R. Casellas and other. Advances in sdn control and telemetry for beyond 100g disaggregated optical networks. *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, 14(6):C23–C37, 2022.